

An aggregate price for energy services: Useful exergy as an intermediate flow in a two-sector model of the economy

João Santos^{a,*}, Tânia Sousa^a, André Serrenho^b, Tiago Domingos^a

^a MARETEC – Marine, Environment and Technology Center, LARSyS, Instituto Superior Técnico, University of Lisbon, Avenida Rovisco Pais, 1, 1049-001 Lisbon, Portugal

^b Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Trumpington Street, Cambridge CB2 1PZ, United Kingdom

ARTICLE INFO

JEL:
Q43
E01
C82
O41
O47
Q41

Keywords:

Useful exergy
National accounts
Energy prices
Economic growth
Extended energy sector

ABSTRACT

Understanding the role of energy in economic growth has been particularly successful when measuring it as useful exergy with, however, the major shortcoming of treating this (intermediate) flow as a primary factor of production. Here, we solve this issue by conceptualizing the economy with an extended energy macro sector (*E*-Sector) encompassing all primary-to-final-to-useful exergy conversions, supplying useful exergy for consumption and as an intermediate to the remaining production processes, considered in the non-energy macro sector (*NE*-Sector). We develop a method for splitting national accounts into these two macro sectors and consider all energy-conversion devices as *E*-Sector capital. This allows us to obtain useful exergy prices, the first time such prices have been obtained consistently for all energy services in an economy, incorporating final-to-useful exergy efficiency, primary exergy supply, and costs of capital and labor used in energy conversion from the primary to the useful stage. As a case study, we consider Portugal (1960–2014), where aggregate useful exergy price declines throughout most of the period, stabilizing in recent years. Periods of decreasing useful exergy prices coincide with economic growth, supporting the strong relation between these two variables, without mistreating useful exergy as a primary factor of production.

1. Introduction

Advances in energy transformation technologies have shaped economic development over the past century. However, mainstream neoclassical growth theory undervalues energy's role in production (Aghion and Howitt, 2009; Kümmel, 1989), viewing the economy as a single sector with only capital and labor as primary inputs, paid according to their marginal productivities.

Numerous studies indicate that the neoclassical approach struggles to explain economic growth, particularly in industrialized countries where exogenous total factor productivity (TFP) is seen as the main growth driver. Efforts to endogenize growth have been unconvincing (van Ark, 2014). By downplaying energy, mainstream models inadequately address the economic impact of energy crises, yet neoclassical assumptions persist in most growth scenarios for climate change policy guidance (Gollier, 2013; Semieniuk et al., 2021; Sousa and Domingos, 2006a).

Alternatives to the neoclassical approach recognize the importance of energy flows by including them in aggregate production functions

(APF) alongside capital and labor, highlighting a strong link between energy use and growth. This is particularly evident in research focused on energy productive for economic end-uses, measured as useful exergy, which captures both the quantity and quality of energy used (Ayres, 2001; Ayres and Warr, 2005; Ayres et al., 1998; Ayres et al., 2003; Ayres et al., 2022; Ayres and Voudouris, 2014; Santos et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2018).

However, even these efforts often fall into the inconsistency of ignoring the nature of energy flows as intermediates transformed and consumed in production processes, and pair them with primary inputs to explain value-added output measures. This is even clearer when working with the exergy metric – which, unlike energy, is actually consumed in each process – and at the useful stage of exergy flows, after all conversion and transformation processes (APS, 2008; Brockway et al., 2016). We propose, with this work, to address this inconsistency by conceptualizing the economy as a multistage energy processing system, in which useful exergy flows are treated both as intermediate inputs to production and as a product sold to consumers.

By implementing the aforementioned framework to a case-study country (Portugal 1960–2014), we will obtain consistent estimates for

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: joao.dos.santos@tecnico.ulisboa.pt (J. Santos).

List of acronyms

APF	Aggregate Production Function
CE	Compensation of Employees
CES	Constant Elasticity of Substitution
CFC	Consumption of Fixed Capital
COFOG	Classification Of the Functions Of Government
COICOP	Classification Of Individual Consumption according to Purpose
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GFCF	Gross Fixed Capital Formation
GOS	Gross Operating Surplus
GVA	Gross Value Added
IAM	Integrated Assessment Model
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
NACE	Nomenclature statistique de las Actividades economicas dans la Communauté Européenne
NEL	Net External Lending
NIL	Net Internal Lending
PIM	Perpetual Inventory Method
ROW	Rest Of World
TFP	Total Factor Productivity

List of variables

$(T - S)_p^E$	Taxes minus Subsidies on production, E-Sector (EUR)
$(T - S)_p^{NE}$	Taxes minus Subsidies on production, NE-Sector (EUR)
$(T - S)_H$	Taxes minus Subsidies on consumption (EUR)
$(T - S)_p$	Taxes minus Subsidies on production (EUR)
C^E	Total Consumption of E-Sector generated Useful Exergy (EUR)
CE^E	Compensation of Employees, E-Sector (EUR)
CE^{NE}	Compensation of Employees, NE-Sector (EUR)
CFC^E	Consumption of Fixed Capital, E-Sector (EUR)
CFC^{NE}	Consumption of Fixed Capital, NE-Sector (EUR)
C_{imp}^E	Imputed Rents associated with E-Sector Investment reclassified from Consumption (EUR)
C^{NE}	Total Consumption of NE-Sector generated goods and services (EUR)
$E_{x,f}$	Final Exergy (MJ)
$E_{x,f}^{0-u}$	Final Exergy consumed in E-Sector activities (MJ)
$E_{x,p}$	Primary Exergy (MJ)
$E_{x,u}$	Useful Exergy (MJ)
$E_{x,u}^{0-u}$	Useful Exergy consumed in E-Sector activities (MJ)
G^E	Government Consumption of E-Sector generated Useful Exergy (EUR)
G^{NE}	Government Consumption of NE-Sector generated goods and services (EUR)
$GOS^{E(GFCF)}$	Gross Operating Surplus allocated from Gross Fixed Capital Formation, E-Sector (EUR)
$GOS^{E(Reclass.)}$	Gross Operating Surplus reclassified from Total Consumption, E-Sector (EUR)
GOS^E	Gross Operating Surplus, E-Sector (EUR)
GOS^{NE}	Gross Operating Surplus, NE-Sector (EUR)
$GVA_{Conv.}^E$	Gross Value Added, E-Sector's Conventional activities (EUR)
GVA^E	Gross Value Added, E-Sector (EUR)
$GVA_{imp.}^E$	Value of end-use devices used in converting final-to-useful exergy (EUR)

GVA^{NE}	Gross Value Added, NE-Sector (EUR)
$GVA_{Supp.}^E$	Gross Value Added, E-Sector's Supplementary activities (EUR)
$I^{E(G)}$	Investment in the E-Sector reclassified from Government Consumption expenditure (EUR)
$I^{E(GFCF)}$	Investment in the E-Sector allocated from Total Gross Fixed Capital Formation (EUR)
$I^{E(P)}$	Investment in the E-Sector reclassified from Private Consumption expenditure (EUR)
I^E	Investment expenditure in the E-Sector (EUR)
I^{NE}	Investment expenditure in the NE-Sector (EUR)
K^E	Capital Stock, E-Sector (EUR)
K^{NE}	Capital Stock, NE-Sector (EUR)
L^E	Human Labour, E-Sector (individuals)
L^{NE}	Human Labour, NE-Sector (individuals)
$M_{Conv.}^E$	Imports to E-Sector Conventional activities (EUR)
M^E	Imports, E-Sector (EUR)
M^{NE}	Imports, NE-Sector (EUR)
$M_{Supp.}^E$	Imports to E-Sector Supplementary activities (EUR)
NIL^E	Net Internal Lending, E-Sector (EUR)
NIL^{NE}	Net Internal Lending, NE-Sector (EUR)
p^E	Private Consumption of E-Sector generated Useful Exergy (EUR)
p^{NE}	Private Consumption of NE-Sector generated goods and services (EUR)
X^E	Exports, E-Sector (EUR)
X^{NE}	Exports, NE-Sector (EUR)
$p_{Ex,u}^{DC}$	Price paid for Useful Exergy directly consumed by households/government (EUR/MJ)
$p_{Ex,u}^{Demand}$	Price paid for Useful Exergy, Total, Demand-Side (EUR/MJ)
$p_{Ex,u}^{INT}$	Price paid for Useful Exergy by NE-Sector activities (EUR/MJ)
$p_{Ex,u}^{Supply}$	Price paid for Useful Exergy, Total, Supply-Side (EUR/MJ)
ΔGov	Government surplus/deficit (EUR)
C	Consumption Expenditure, Total, National Accounts (EUR)
C'	Consumption Expenditure, Total, Two-Sector Model (EUR)
CE	Compensation of Employees, Total (EUR)
CFC	Consumption of Fixed Capital, Total (EUR)
GOS	Gross Operating Surplus, Total, National Accounts (EUR)
GOS'	Gross Operating Surplus, Total, Two-Sector Model (EUR)
GVA	Gross Value Added, Total (EUR)
I	Investment Expenditure, Total, National Accounts (EUR)
I'	Investment Expenditure, Total, Two-Sector Model (EUR)
INT	NE-Sector payments to E-Sector for intermediate Useful Exergy (EUR)
K	Capital Stock, Total (EUR)
L	Human Labour, Total (individuals)
M	Imports, Total (EUR)
NEL	Net External Lending, Total (EUR)
NIL	Net Internal Lending, Total (EUR)
Q	Gross Domestic Product, Total, National Accounts (EUR)
Q'	Gross Domestic Product, Total, Two-Sector Model (EUR)
Sav.	Household Savings (EUR)
X	Exports, Total (EUR)
d	annual constant capital stock depreciation rate (%)

the price paid for useful exergy in this economy. Price estimates obtained in this way are more consistent than previous efforts to compute prices for energy services based on the combination of fuel prices and energy efficiencies alone (Stehrer and Sabouniha, 2023; Fouquet and Pearson, 2006; Haas et al., 2008; Howarth, 1997). Useful exergy price estimates generated with the proposed model incorporate changes in final-to-useful exergy efficiency, primary energy supply, and the costs of capital and labor used in converting final-to-useful exergy. Comparing these price estimates with trends in gross domestic product (GDP) provides a good tracker with economic growth.

This work is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the theoretical and empirical background. Section 3 presents our conceptualization of a two-sector economic model, while Section 4 details its implementation for Portugal (1960–2014), based on reclassified national accounts and energy/exergy balances. Section 5 discusses the results, and Section 6 concludes with future work hypotheses.

2. Background and theoretical perspective

2.1. Neoclassical growth theory and its limitations

The mathematical foundation of neoclassical growth theory is a differentiable, homogeneous aggregate production function that combines inputs (capital and labor) with economic output (e.g., GDP). National accounting databases enabled quantitative time-series analyses (Abramovitz, 1956; Fabricant, 1954; Kendrick, 1961), revealing that capital and labor alone could not explain historical GDP growth in industrialized countries. Instead, total factor productivity (TFP) emerged as the major unexplained source of GDP growth (Easterly and Levine, 2001; Solow, 1956; Solow, 1957; Swan, 1956).

Efforts to explain growth endogenously have led to models with increasing returns to scale due to knowledge accumulation spillovers (Lains, 2004; Romer, 1986), providing important insights (Aghion et al., 1998; Grossman and Helpman, 1994; Jones and Manuelli, 1990; Rebelo, 1991; Sala-i-Martin and Barro, 1995; Weitzman, 1998). However, key variables like “knowledge” are difficult to quantify. Similar critiques apply to linking exogenous growth to hard-to-measure factors like information and communication technology (ICT) (Bergeaud et al., 2017), institutions, or entrepreneurship (Acs et al., 2014).

Both desired (technical/organizational innovation) and undesired (errors, omitted variables, aggregation bias) components are included in the exogenous part of economic growth (Hulten, 2001). Some research has reduced this residual (Crafts, 2009; Koszerek et al., 2007) by improving capital (Griliches and Jorgenson, 1966; Solow, 1962) and labor (Denison, 1962; Denison, 1967) measurements. However, even with qualitative adjustments to production factors, broader investment concepts, or knowledge spillovers, most of the residual remains unexplained (US Energy Information Administration (US EIA), 2011).

Unable to explain growth in terms of economic variables, neoclassical approaches also fail to do so in terms of physical variables. Energy is either never mentioned, or its role is downplayed, severing the connection between the economy and the physical world (Sousa and Domingos, 2006a; Sousa and Domingos, 2006b).

This neglect arises from the neoclassical assumption that firms pay for inputs in proportion to their marginal products. Consequently, payments to factors in national accounts should reflect their productivities (Gans et al., 2014). Since most payments go to capital and labor, these are viewed as the only significant factors. Payments for energy, associated with extractive industries and agriculture, constitute a small percentage of GDP,¹ justifying its omission as a production factor (Aghion and Howitt, 2009; Kümmel and Lindenberger, 2014).

¹ Around 4 % w/o agriculture; at most 10 % w/ agriculture (Denison, 2010; Platchkov and Pollitt, 2011; US Energy Information Administration (US EIA), 2011).

Downplaying energy complicates explanations for economic recessions during energy crises.² Furthermore, growth scenarios used in climate policy through Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) assume that absolute energy-GDP decoupling is feasible and inexpensive (Gollier, 2013; Stanton et al., 2009), relying on controversial aggregate production functions with an exogenous term as the sole driver of growth (Semieniuk et al., 2021).

2.2. Energy as a factor of production

Energy’s role in mainstream models has been challenged since the 1970s’ “Limits to Growth” report (Meadows et al., 1974). Subsequent work emphasized energy as essential to production, alongside capital and labor, in aggregate production functions (APF) (Allen et al., 1976; Dasgupta and Heal, 1979; Hudson and Jorgenson, 1978; Jorgenson, 1978; Solow, 1974; Stern and Kander, 2012). Despite assuming production is impossible without energy, constant elasticities of substitution permit production with negligible energy inputs if capital and labor compensate.

Energy is downplayed in these models because they equate factor productivity with cost shares. The heterodox “biophysical school” challenges this neoclassical assumption, arguing that energy is a fundamental non-substitutable input (Cleveland, 1992; Cleveland et al., 1984; Costanza, 1992; Costanza and Herendeen, 1984; Kaufmann, 1992). Inspired by Georgescu-Roegen (Georgescu-Roegen, 1971), this school goes as far as modelling growth considering energy as the sole input, without capital or labor.

A more grounded approach acknowledges that energy is productive only when used to fuel capital and labor. In capital-labor-energy APFs—bypassing the neoclassical cost-share theorem—historical growth is explained without a residual, though output elasticities differ significantly from cost shares (Ayres and Warr, 2005; Kümmel et al., 2000; Lindenberger and Kummel, 2002; Tintner et al., 1977).

Correlation between energy use and economic growth does not establish causality. Statistical tests assessing whether GDP changes follow energy use changes, or vice versa (Granger, 1969; Toda and Yamamoto, 1995) have been conducted (Odhiambo, 2010; Ozturk, 2010; Payne, 2010), but they disagree on causality direction and its implications for energy policy.

One factor influencing causality tests is how energy flows are measured (Warr and Ayres, 2010). Traditional 1st law analysis ignores irreversibilities in energy conversion and does not account for energy quality (Dincer and Rosen, 2012). The appropriate metric is useful exergy, not primary or final energy—Fig. 1. Exergy reflects thermodynamic energy quality: its potential to perform work during economic production as it reaches equilibrium with the environment (Reistad, 1975). Like energy, exergy flows through conversion processes, becoming productive at the useful stage before delivering energy services. Unlike energy, exergy serves as a consistent metric for energy and material flows³ (APS, 2008; Brockway et al., 2016; Sousa et al., 2017) and is consumed in production. In Fig. 1, primary energy/exergy in natural resources (coal) is transformed into electricity in a power station and delivered to consumers. It is further converted to a useful form (heat) for end-use devices (electric heaters), providing energy services (thermal comfort).

Increasing data availability from societal-level exergy analysis

² According to the cost-share theorem, if energy accounts for 5 % of total payments, the 1973–1975 oil shocks, which reduced US energy input by 5.2 %, should have led to a 0.26 % decrease in US output. However, the actual decrease was four times greater (Kümmel et al., 2008).

³ For example, 1 kWh of energy as heat at 30 °C has lower quality than as mechanical work. The latter can convert into up to 1 kWh of 30 °C heat, but the former can only convert to a maximum of 0.066 kWh of work (assuming a 10 °C environment).

Fig. 1. Energy and exergy flows in the economy. Source: (Santos et al., 2021).

(Marshall et al., 2024; Pinto et al., 2023; Serrenho et al., 2014; Serrenho et al., 2016; Warr and Ayres, 2010) has enabled applications that provide crucial economic and sustainability insights (Ayres et al., 1998; Brockway et al., 2014; Court, 2019; Ecclesia et al., 2022; Felício et al., 2019; Guevara et al., 2016; Kümmel et al., 2010; Sciubba, 2019; Warr et al., 2008; Whiting et al., 2017). Strong causality from useful exergy consumption to economic output is observed via APF (Aramendia et al., 2021; Ayres et al., 2022; Ayres and Voudouris, 2014; Brockway et al., 2017; Heun et al., 2017; Koszerek et al., 2007; Nieto et al., 2021; Sakai et al., 2018; Warr and Ayres, 2006), confirming a gap between energy’s productive power and its cost share. A significant portion of long-run economic growth can be effectively represented by changes in final-to-useful exergy efficiency (Santos et al., 2021).

However, many approaches that include useful exergy as a production factor in APFs inconsistently overlook that energy flows are intermediates in production while using value-added measures for economic output.

2.3. The economy as an energy processing system

Energy has a dual role in production: as an intermediate input, e.g. in metallurgical/chemical processes; as a final product, used directly for space heating, lighting, etc.

Neoclassical theory “hides” intermediates within a single-sector framework, aggregating many firms producing a composite good using only capital and labor inputs.⁴ This simplification fails in the real world, where price-taking firms aim to minimize costs of capital, labor, and intermediates. Just as direct capital (labor) costs do not reflect complementary labor (capital) costs, energy costs do not account for the capital/labor needed to use energy productively. Although producing intermediates does not add value to output, the neoclassical view of firms relying solely on capital and labor cannot be generalized to the entire economy.

Research that includes energy as an independent production factor in aggregate production functions (APFs) overlooks the nature of energy flows as intermediates. This inconsistency also applies to studies using the useful exergy metric, with exceptions: a previous paper (Santos

⁴ Picture a bakery, producing bread from capital (oven) and labor (the baker), but no flour or fuel (Mankiw, 1997).

et al., 2018) concludes that the three-factor formulation (capital, labor, useful exergy) is inappropriate when using proper statistical methods for identifying energy-dependent value-added Cobb-Douglas APFs.

This inconsistency can be resolved by using a gross output measure that includes the value of intermediates as the dependent variable in APFs (Kander and Stern, 2014). However, this approach requires more data, especially regarding prices for intermediate inputs.⁵

To address these issues consistently, the economy must be reimagined as a multi-sector materials-energy processing system with inter-industry feedback (Ayres, 2001; Ayres and Warr, 2005), where final products arise from a chain of intermediates rather than directly from raw materials or capital/labor alone. Recent work by Carey King (King, 2020; King, 2022) recognizes useful energy as an intermediate, connecting energy resource extraction to the production of goods and services. A multi-sector production process acknowledges intermediates and alters the neoclassical view of factor productivities equating cost shares, without changing the value-added identity. By integrating sectoral analysis into a broader biophysical framework, this approach highlights the interconnectedness of energy, industrial, and service activities. Effective economic and energy policies must consider these interdependencies, especially during structural changes or resource constraints. If the primary sector encompasses all extraction and transformation of “raw” exergy into useful exergy, payments from the secondary sector for intermediates can estimate useful exergy prices in the economy.

2.4. Prices for energy services/useful exergy

Ayres and Warr (Ayres, 2001; Ayres and Warr, 2005) have long argued, based on qualitative historical evidence, that the declining cost of useful exergy, or energy services, has significantly driven economic growth in industrialized countries, at least until recently.

It has been suggested that energy price trends are useful but not reliable indicators of resource scarcity, as they do not reflect the consumer’s burden or incentives. Nordhaus (Nordhaus, 1996) highlighted the danger of focusing on energy prices instead of energy services,

⁵ Only electric power is treated as a commodity with financial accounts, while motive power and space heat produced and consumed across various economic activities, including households, lack explicit market prices.

showing that this perspective overlooks technological advancements and significantly underestimates the decline in lighting costs over the last 200 years, along with the resulting consumer welfare.

Consumers are more interested in the services generated (heat, power, transport, light) than in the amount of energy used. When technology efficiency improves, service prices fall, even if energy prices remain unchanged. Fouquet (Fouquet, 2011; Fouquet and Pearson, 2006) provided extensive evidence on long-term trends in energy service prices and consumption. In later papers, he emphasized the risks of focusing on energy prices instead of energy service prices. He used energy service price estimates to calculate income and price elasticities of demand for domestic heating, passenger transport, and lighting in the UK over two centuries (Fouquet, 2014). He concluded that energy service prices significantly incentivized energy transitions and that these trends could help identify future energy use and carbon dioxide emissions trends (Fouquet, 2016).

Fouquet and other authors (Haas et al., 2008; Howarth, 1997) convert fuel prices into energy service equivalents by combining final energy prices with the efficiency of the equipment used. However, they face issues of unit comparability and aggregation, estimating the prices of different energy services (e.g., lighting, heating, transportation) in various units (e.g., lumens, thermal units, kilometers). They also use different metrics for energy quality, such as lumens per watt-hour for lighting and kilometers per unit of fuel for transportation. This complicates comparisons across services and aggregating them into a common index, potentially obscuring each service's price dynamics over time. In contrast, focusing on the useful stage of energy flows in exergy terms allows for measuring the exergy used in providing services in consistent units (Joules), enabling comparable aggregation across different end-uses.

Fouquet and others' energy service price estimates consider changes in the costs of primary and final energy resources (e.g., wood, coal, oil, electricity), the costs of capital and technology required to convert these resources into usable energy (e.g., stoves, lamps, engines), and advancements in passive systems (e.g., trains) that transform usable energy into services over time (Tostes et al., 2024). However, they do not explicitly account for the costs of human labor involved in delivering energy services.

Estimating prices for useful energy and useful exergy involves different concepts and implications. Pricing useful energy refers to the energy utilized for services in a specific context without considering the quality of energy delivered or the efficiency of conversion processes. In contrast, pricing useful exergy is more logical, as it allows for direct comparison and aggregation, expressed as monetary value per exergy content (potential to perform work), regardless of the energy carrier or end-use. While pricing useful energy may yield similar units for different end-uses, these prices are not directly comparable since they overlook energy quality and degradation in each process – see Fig. 1.⁶ Thus, pricing useful energy faces similar critiques as Fouquet's work.

Implementing the two-sector model in the next section for a real economy will yield a consistent estimate for energy service prices, incorporating final-to-useful exergy efficiency, primary energy supply, and costs of capital and labor in conversion. This will measure the useful stage of energy conversion using a common unit, exergy. The results will provide quantitative evidence to support Ayres and Warr's (Ayres, 2001; Ayres and Warr, 2005) claim that declining energy service prices drive long-term growth, without inconsistently treating useful exergy as a primary production factor.

⁶ E.g., the price for useful energy from electricity may be the same for light and heat, but the useful exergy price will be higher for heating due to its lower energy quality.

3. Model conceptualization

Fig. 2 illustrates the conceptual framework, depicting production as a two-stage process that separates energy conversion activities from other productive activities. Expenditure flows represent money spent on goods and services (including useful exergy), while income flows represent payments for factors of production (e.g., wages for labor and rents for capital).

The extended energy macro sector (E-Sector) encompasses all primary-to-final-to-useful energy/exergy conversion processes across economic activities, beyond traditional energy industries. It aggregates traditional energy processes that convert primary exergy ($E_{x,p}$) from the environment to final exergy ($E_{x,f}$) sold to consumers. Additionally, it includes conversions from final to useful exergy ($E_{x,u}$) in end-use devices (e.g., automobiles), wherever they occur in the economy. An end-use device is any device actively converting energy/exergy from the final to useful stage (e.g., a lightbulb converting electricity to light, or a truck converting gasoline to mechanical drive). Passive systems, like buildings, are not considered end-use devices, though heating systems within them are.⁷

Despite the nomenclature adopted for the non-energy sector, all economic activities in our framework consume energy. The boundary of the extended E-Sector allows us to conceptualize most economic activities as “having a foot in both camps”, in the sense that they feature both energy conversion processes to the useful exergy stage and non-energy converting processes that combine useful exergy with capital and/or labor to provide a service. Fig. 3 illustrates some examples, e.g. a lightbulb used in a bank converts final exergy (electricity) into useful exergy (light) and lies within the boundary for the E-Sector (along with the conversion processes that transformed primary exergy from coal into final exergy as electricity). Useful exergy generated as light within the E-Sector is delivered – within the economic activity banks – to the remaining processes which lie within the boundary of the NE-Sector, e.g. illuminating the room in which a loan officer is working in. Similar examples can be invoked in other economic activities (e.g. Construction) and households and government.

Despite being represented in our framework within the boundaries of the macro E-Sector, the output of end-use devices is used in every economic activity, in households and in the government. Useful exergy converted in these end-use devices is the intermediate between E-Sector and NE-Sector (or a consumption expenditure by households, government). Thus, in our conceptual framework every economic activity is energy-using. Although most economic activities have “a foot in both camps” as shown in Fig. 3, exception is made of economic activities that lie entirely within the boundaries of the E-Sector – see Fig. 4. These economic activities actively participate in the conversion of primary-to-final-to-useful exergy, but they also consume final/useful exergy themselves (E-Sector own-uses).

The E-Sector produces useful exergy for economic activities, powered by capital stock (K^E) and human labor (L^E). Payments to these factors are represented as gross operating surplus (GOS^E) and compensation of employees (CE^E). A fraction γ of useful exergy is used in production in the NE-Sector ($0 < \gamma < 1$), while its complement ($1 - \gamma$) is consumed directly in households/government, corresponding to a consumption expenditure (C^E). The transition from green to red arrow in Fig. 2 shows this same flow in physical units (Joule, green) and monetary units (EURO, red), with the conversion implying a price⁸ – Eq. (1).

$$C^E = P_{E_{x,u}}^{DC} \cdot (1 - \gamma) \cdot E_{x,u} \tag{1}$$

Besides useful exergy, for which the NE-Sector pays the E-Sector

⁷ Our definitions for end-use devices, active and passive systems are the same as in (Dasgupta and Heal, 1979).

⁸ DC stands for Direct Consumption.

Fig. 2. The economy as an energy-processing two-sector model, with an extended energy sector (E-Sector), and a non-energy sector (NE-Sector). Red: expenditure money flows; Blue: income money flows; Green: exergy flows, in physical units. Purple: intermediate money flows. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Examples of how the boundary for the extended energy sector (E-Sector) is imagined, to encompass final-to-useful exergy converting processes within each economic activity (as well as households and government).

(INT), NE-Sector production is powered by capital (K^{NE}) and labor (L^{NE}), paid with gross operating surplus (GOS^{NE}) and compensation of employees (CE^{NE}), respectively. Both macro sectors pay net taxes on production (taxes T minus subsidies S) to the government – see Figure 5.

Fig. 4 presents a detailed E-Sector diagram based on NACE classifications.⁹ The conventional energy activities include Mining & Quarrying

(NACE B), Electricity, Gas, Steam, and Air Conditioning Supply (NACE D), and Manufacture of Coke and Refined Petroleum Products (NACE C19). Additionally, the extended E-Sector incorporates supplementary economic activities such as Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing (NACE A) and the Manufacture of Food, Beverages, and Tobacco Products (NACE C10–12) because they are involved in the conversion chain that generates useful exergy as muscle work from food and feed carriers. The aforementioned E-Sector activities are entirely located within the E-Sector boundary. Hence, investment in both active and passive systems for these economic activities is considered investment in the E-Sector, since it aids in primary-to-final-to-useful exergy conversion. Although forestry and the

⁹ Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne. A list of NACE categories is provided in Appendix A.

Fig. 4. Detail of extended energy macro sector. Red: expenditure money flows; Blue: income money flows; Green: exergy flows, in physical units. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

manufacture of alcoholic beverages or tobacco do not contribute directly to food production, they are grouped with agricultural and food manufacturing activities for this initial model iteration. Distinguishing standard NACE categories to accurately represent these activities would complicate the analysis and is beyond the current scope, but it should be addressed in future versions.

Conventional industries convert primary exergy ($E_{x,p}$) into final exergy ($E_{x,f}$). Final exergy – discounting own uses of both conventional/supplement E-Sector activities ($E_{x,f}^{o-u}$), which is converted into useful exergy to be consumed by these activities themselves ($E_{x,u}^{o-u}$) – is supplied to end-use devices (wherever they may be found in the economy i.e., within industries or households) to be converted to useful exergy ($E_{x,u}$). All economic activities in the two-sector model consume useful exergy. The useful exergy flowing from the E-Sector to NE-Sector production or direct household and government consumption discounts for the exergy generated and used within the E-Sector.

The gross value added (GVA) of conventional and supplement activities, combined with the monetary value of end-use devices¹⁰ converting final-to-useful exergy (GVA_{Imp}^E), forms the total GVA for the E-Sector (GVA^E).

The two-sector economic framework requires reclassifying national accounts and energy balances to ensure consistency with the model’s variables.

The national accounts’ central identity ensures that the three GDP measurement approaches—expenditure, income, and output—yield the same result. Focusing on the first two, this identity is shown in Eq. (2), where the l.h.s. represents expenditure, the r.h.s. represents income, and Q is GDP. Total consumption expenditure C is the sum of private (P) and government (G) consumption expenditure.

$$C + I + X - M = Q = GOS + CE + (T - S)_p \quad (2)$$

The NE-Sector output, from an expenditure perspective, includes non-energy goods/services consumed by households and government (C^{NE}) and total investment I , divided between the NE-Sector (I^{NE}) and E-Sector (I^E). Each macro sector has a trade balance (exports X minus imports M). Total economic output (Q) equals NE-Sector output plus the monetary value of useful exergy consumed by households/government (C^E). From an income perspective, Q is the sum of payments to capital and labor in both macro sectors ($GOS^{NE,E}$, $CE^{NE,E}$), plus net taxes paid to

the government $(T - S)_p^{NE,E}$. While applying the two-sector model requires reclassifying national accounts on both sides, the central identity must hold – Eq. (3).

$$(C^{NE} + C^E) + (I^{NE} + I^E) + (X^{NE} + X^E) - (M^{NE} + M^E) = Q = (GOS^{NE} + GOS^E) + (CE^{NE} + CE^E) + (T - S)_p^{NE} + (T - S)_p^E \quad (3)$$

Due to reclassification, total output for the two-sector model (Q) may differ from gross domestic product (GDP) reported in national accounts, as explained in Section 4.

In addition to the central identity in Eq. (3), national account reclassification must ensure that monetary flows entering and exiting each economic agent match. This is illustrated in the circular flow diagram in Fig. 5.

The represented economic agents are households, government, banks, firms, and the rest of the world (ROW). The identities governing each agent are listed below. Each firm is split between processes that consume final exergy and convert it to useful exergy (E) and production activities that consume useful exergy (NE), represented by the intermediate (INT) arrow.

• **Households:**

$$P^{NE} + P^E + Sav. + (T - S)_H = GOS^{NE} + GOS^E + CE^{NE} + CE^E \quad (4)$$

• **Government:**

$$G^{NE} + G^E + \Delta Gov = (T - S)_H + (T - S)_p^{NE} + (T - S)_p^E \quad (5)$$

• **Banks:**

$$NEL + NIL^{NE} + NIL^E = Sav. + \Delta Gov \quad (6)$$

• **Firms (E):**

$$GOS^E + CE^E + (T - S)_p^E + I^E = P^E + G^E + NIL^E + (X^E - M^E) + INT \quad (7)$$

• **Firms (NE)**

$$GOS^{NE} + CE^{NE} + (T - S)_p^{NE} + INT = P^{NE} + G^{NE} + NIL^{NE} + I^E + (X^{NE} - M^{NE}) \quad (8)$$

¹⁰ E.g., the costs of expenditure on end-use devices.

Fig. 5. Circular flow diagram for the two-sector model. All arrows represent money flows. Red: expenditure; Blue: income; Purple: intermediate. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

• ROW:

$$(X^{NE} - M^{NE}) + (X^E - M^E) = NEL \tag{9}$$

Households are paid from firms, for capital and labor they provide (GOS^{NE} , GOS^E , CE^{NE} , CE^E), and they spend on private consumption of NE-Sector goods/services (P^{NE}), and E-Sector useful exergy (P^E), pay net taxes on consumption to the government $(T - S)_H$, and inject savings in the banks¹¹ ($Sav.$) – Eq. (4). Government receives net taxes from households and firms $(T - S)_p^{E,NE}$, and spends on government consumption of NE-Sector goods/services (G^{NE}), and E-Sector useful exergy (G^E), injecting the difference ΔGov in the banks¹² – Eq. (5). Banks take households’ savings and add/subtract government surplus/deficit ΔGov , and use it to balance net internal lending for firms ($NIL^{E,NE}$), and net external lending (NEL) with the rest of the world – Eq. (6). The NEL to the rest of the world is equal to the combined trade balance of the E-Sector ($X^E - M^E$) and NE-Sector ($X^{NE} - M^{NE}$) – Eq. (9). Firms (NE) receive private and government consumption expenditure on goods/services provided ($P^{NE} + G^{NE} = C^{NE}$), net internal lending from banks (NIL^{NE}), investment expenditure from the E-Sector firms (I^E), and the corresponding trade balance ($X^{NE} - M^{NE}$), and they spend on payments to households ($GOS^{NE} + CE^{NE}$), net taxes to government $(T - S)_p^{NE}$, intermediate payments to the E-Sector for useful exergy (INT), and investment expenditure in themselves (I^{NE}) – Eq. (8). Finally, firms (E) receive private and government consumption expenditure on useful

exergy ($P^E + G^E = C^E$), net internal lending from banks (NIL^E), intermediate payment for useful exergy provided to the NE-Sector (INT), and the corresponding trade balance ($X^E - M^E$); and they spend on payments to households ($GOS^E + CE^E$), net taxes to government $(T - S)_p^E$, and investment from the NE-Sector (I^E). This closes the circular flow in the two-sector model – Eq. (7).

The next subsections detail the disaggregation and reclassification of national accounts of the expenditure and income components in Eq. (3).

4. Materials and methods

4.1. Reclassification of national accounts

4.1.1. Expenditure

4.1.1.1. Consumption. Total consumption (C) is the sum of private (P) and government (G) consumption expenditure.

The UN Statistics Division categorizes consumption by purpose (COICOP) and government consumption by function (COFOG). Both classifications are organized into Divisions, Groups (the highest level considered here), Classes, and Subclasses. A detailed list of all COICOP/COFOG Divisions and Groups can be found in Appendix A.

The correspondence between COICOP/COFOG categories and the two-sector model variables (Table 1) is as follows: 1) expenditure on energy carriers (e.g., food, fuels) is classified as useful exergy consumption by households (P^E) or government (G^E); 2) expenditure on non-energy goods/services (e.g., clothing, education services) is classified as consumption by households (P^{NE}) or government (G^{NE}) in the NE-Sector; 3) expenditure on goods that convert final-to-useful exergy is

¹¹ The box labeled “Banks” in Fig. 5 represents only the financial transactions in markets between economic agents. The banks themselves are treated as firms split between (E) and (NE) processes. Consumption of useful exergy by banks is therefore included in the intermediate payments from Firms (NE) to Firms (E) – purple arrow in Fig. 5.

¹² If $\Delta Gov > 0$ there is government surplus injected in the financial markets. If $\Delta Gov < 0$ there is government deficit and the government must borrow money from the financial markets.

Table 1

Allocation of private and government consumption expenditure from national account in the two-sector model. COICOP/COFOG categories containing goods corresponding to more than one of the two-sector model's variables are split in half.

Two-sector model expenditure	Consumption Classification Divisions/Groups
P^E	(COICOP) Divisions: 01, 02; Groups: 04.5
P^{NE}	(COICOP) Divisions: 03, 10–12; Groups: 04.1–04.4, 05.2, 05.6, 06.2–06.3, 07.2–07.3, 08.1, 08.3, 09.3–09.6
G^E	(COFOG) Groups: 04.3
G^{NE}	(COFOG) Divisions: 01–03, 05, 08–10; Groups: 04.1–04.2, 04.4, 04.5–04.6 (50 %), 06.1–06.3, 06.5–06.6, 06.4 (50 %), 07.1 (50 %), 07.2–07.6
$I^{E(P)}$	(COICOP) Groups: 05.1, 05.3–05.5, 06.1, 07.1, 08.2, 09.1–09.2
$I^{E(G)}$	(COFOG) Groups: 04.5–04.6 (50 %), 06.4 (50 %), 07.1 (50 %)

reclassified as investment expenditure in the E-Sector¹³ ($I^{E(P)}$, $I^{E(G)}$).

This point is justified because purchasing these goods enhances the E-Sector's capacity to generate useful exergy from final energy/exergy, constituting investment expenditure to increase its output.

When reclassifying consumer goods as investment expenditure, we must add the imputed rents from newly defined investment items to the consumption expenditure for directly consumed useful exergy ($C^{E(imp.)}$). Imputed rents are calculated from the gross operating surplus of these reclassified investment categories – Section 4.1.3.

Total consumption expenditure, in the two-sector model (C), is given by:

$$C = C^{NE} + C^E \quad (10)$$

With:

$$C^E = P^E + G^E + C^{E(imp.)}, \text{ for the E – Sector} \quad (11)$$

And:

$$C^{NE} = P^{NE} + G^{NE}, \text{ for the NE – Sector} \quad (12)$$

4.1.1.2. Investment. Investment expenditure is measured in national accounts as gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), typically disaggregated by asset type.

Table 2 shows the correspondence between GFCF by asset type in each economic (NACE) activity and the two-sector model variables. Most assets that convert energy/exergy from primary to final to useful stages (e.g., transport equipment) are categorized as E-Sector investment ($I^{E(GFCF)}$), regardless of the economic activity. These assets enhance the E-Sector's capacity to generate useful exergy. In activities within the E-Sector (e.g., *Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing* – NACE A), all assets are also classified as E-Sector investment.

Total investment expenditure, in the two-sector model, is given by:

$$I = I^{NE} + I^E \quad (13)$$

With, for the E-Sector:

$$I^E = I^{E(GFCF)} + I^{E(P)} + I^{E(G)} \quad (14)$$

¹³ The superscripts (P) and (G) indicate whether the reclassified investment originated from private or government consumption categories e.g., privately owned automobiles are reclassified from private consumption expenditure to investment expenditure in the E-Sector $I^{E(P)}$. Corporate automobiles are already classified as investment expenditure in national accounts, and their allocation to the E-Sector is conducted in the next subsection. However, medical appliances such as dialysis machines purchased by public hospitals are reclassified from government consumption expenditure to investment expenditure in the E-Sector $I^{E(G)}$.

Table 2

Allocation of GFCF from national accounts, by type of asset and NACE activity, in the two-sector model. The (GFCF) superscript distinguishes investment expenditure in the E-Sector allocated from national accounts GFCF from private $I^{E(P)}$ or government $I^{E(G)}$ consumption expenditure in national accounts (see Table 1).

Two-sector model expenditure	NACE economic activity	Gross fixed capital formation by type of asset
$I^{E(GFCF)}$	A, B, C10–12, C19, D	All types of assets
	All other NACE	Transport equipment (TraEq); Computer hardware (IT); Communication equipment (CT); Cultivated assets (Cult); Other machinery, equipment & weapons (OMach 50 %)
	A, B, C10–12, C19, D	No assets
		Dwellings (RStruc); Other buildings & structures (OCon); Computer software & databases (Soft_DB); Research & Development (RD); Other intellectual property products (OIPP); Other machinery, equipment & weapons (OMach 50 %)
I^{NE}	All other NACE	

4.1.1.3. Exports/imports. Exports and imports of goods/services are disaggregated by NACE economic activity.

Trade balance in the identified conventional and supplement NACE activities – Table 3 – is allocated to the E-Sector. All remaining trade is allocated to the NE-Sector.

4.1.2. Factors of production

4.1.2.1. Capital. In national accounts, capital stocks for each year (K_t) are calculated using the perpetual inventory method (PIM), which adds current investment expenditure (I_t) to the previous year's capital stock (K_{t-1}) and subtracts current consumption of fixed capital (CFC_t) – Eq. (15). CFC is determined by multiplying the previous year's capital stock by a constant depreciation rate d .

$$K_t = K_{t-1} + I_t - CFC_t = K_{t-1} + I_t - d \bullet K_{t-1} \quad (15)$$

The PIM in Eq. (15) calculates aggregate capital stock using a common or asset-specific constant annual depreciation rate. The steady-state approach (Berlemann and Wesselhöft, 2014) can be used to obtain an initial capital stock value – Eq. (16).

$$K_{t-1} = \frac{I_t}{g_{GDP} + d} \quad (16)$$

In Eq. (16), annual GDP growth (g_{GDP}) is generally the average of the first three years. After determining initial capital stock, Eq. (15) is applied to obtain the annual capital stock time series.

Capital stock correspondence by asset type and NACE economic activity with inputs to the E-Sector or NE-Sector follows the same method as for investment expenditure (Table 2). Annual time series for capital stock by asset type (i) and NACE activity (j) are constructed using the PIM – Eq. (17).

$$K_t^{ij} = K_{t-1}^{ij} + I_t^{ij} - d^i \bullet K_{t-1}^{ij} \quad (17)$$

Table 3

Allocation of trade in the two-sector model, by NACE economic activity.

Two-sector model trade	NACE economic activity	
X^E, M^E	Conventional	B, C19, D
	Supplement	A, C10–12
X^{NE}, M^{NE}		All other NACE

Where d^i represents the annual constant depreciation rate for asset type i . The initial capital stock value for asset type i in NACE economic activity j is determined using the steady-state approach - Eq. (18).

$$K_{t-1}^{ij} = \frac{I_t^{ij}}{g_{GDP} + d^i} \quad (18)$$

Reclassified investment expenditure from consumption (Table 1) is labeled by asset type (Table 4) before applying the perpetual inventory method (PIM). The depreciation rate for capital stock from reclassified investment items matches that of the corresponding asset type (Table 4).

4.1.2.2. *Labor.* Labor inputs (L) are measured by the number of engaged individuals, including employees and self-employed.

Labor is disaggregated by NACE activity (Table 5). Employment in conventional and supplementary NACE activities is allocated to the E -Sector (L^E), while all remaining employment is assigned to the NE -Sector (L^{NE}).

4.1.3. *Income*

4.1.3.1. *Gross operating surplus.* Payments to capital are accounted as gross operating surplus (GOS) in national accounts, which typically includes imputed compensation for self-employed individuals. However, we adjust GOS to classify these payments to self-employed individuals as labor compensation.

Gross operating surplus (GOS) is usually reported only at an aggregate level, not by asset type or activity. However, the share of GOS by asset type (i) and economic activity (j) in total GOS can be equated with the corresponding share of consumption of fixed capital (CFC) in total CFC - Eq. (19).¹⁴

$$GOS_{ij}^{(GFCF)} = \left(\sum_{ij} GOS \right) \cdot \frac{CFC_{ij}}{\sum_{ij} CFC} \quad (19)$$

Where CFC for each asset type (i) in each economic activity (j) is calculated by multiplying the capital stock by the corresponding annual

Table 4

Reclassification of national accounts' private and government consumption expenditure items as investment expenditure in the two-sector model, by type of asset.

Two-sector model expenditure	Consumption Classification Divisions/ Groups	Type of asset
$I^{E(P)}$	(COICOP) Groups: 05.1, 05.3–05.5, 09.2 (COICOP) Groups: 07.1 (COICOP) Groups: 08.2, 09.1 (COFOG) Groups: 06.4, 07.1	Other machinery, equipment & weapons (OMach) Transport equipment (TraEq) Communication equipment (CT) Other machinery, equipment & weapons (OMach)
$I^{E(G)}$	(COFOG) Groups: 04.5 (COFOG) Groups: 04.6	Transport equipment (TraEq) Communication equipment (CT)

¹⁴ Economic activities with high depreciation typically have high capital intensity, and hence higher payments to capital as well (Alvarez-Cuadrado et al., 2018; Gallardo-Albarrán and Inklaar, 2021). The ratio of capital payments to depreciation is assumed constant across asset types and economic activities – a stability that is observed in the real world (Doms and Dunne, 1998; Mazzucato, 2011). Of course, this is still a rough estimate given that different sectors have different asset structures and income-generating capabilities e.g., high CFC but low GOS due to high operational costs or low profitability. But, in the absence of more granular data, it is a practical and reasonable approach.

Table 5

Allocation of employment in the two-sector model, by NACE economic activity.

Two-sector model employment	NACE economic activity
L^E	A, B, C10–12, C19, D
L^{NE}	All other NACE

depreciation rate.

The approach in Eq. (19) applies to investment expenditure from national accounts (superscript GFCF). For investment reclassified from consumption expenditure, GOS is estimated by equating it directly to the corresponding CFC for that asset type in that economic activity.

GOS allocation between the two sectors follows the same rule as investment expenditure or capital stocks. Total GOS for the two-sector model is given by:

$$GOS' = GOS^{NE} + GOS^E \quad (20)$$

With:

$$GOS^E = GOS^{E(GFCF)} + GOS^{E(Reclass.)} \quad (21)$$

Total GOS from national accounts equals $GOS^{NE} + GOS^{E(GFCF)}$, indicating that total GOS in the two-sector model is higher due to payments to capital reclassified from consumption expenditure ($GOS^{E(Reclass.)}$). To ensure both expenditure and income approaches yield the same result, a component of imputed rents from this reclassified capital is included in consumption expenditure ($C^{E(imp.)}$), making Eq. (22) hold.

$$GOS^{E(Reclass.)} = C^{E(imp.)} \quad (22)$$

4.1.3.2. *Compensation of employees.* Payments to labor are recorded as compensation of employees (CE) in national accounts, including both employee salaries and self-employed income (the latter deducted from GOS).

Labor payments are disaggregated by NACE activity (Table 6). Compensation for employees and self-employed in conventional and supplemental NACE activities is allocated to the E -Sector (CE^E), while the remaining payments are allocated to the NE -Sector (CE^{NE}).

4.1.3.3. *Net taxes on production and imports.* The third component of the GDP income approach is net taxes on production and imports ($(T - S)_p$, typically reported only at the aggregate level.

Payments to capital (GOS) and labor (CE) by NACE activity allow the computation of gross value added (GVA) for each activity by summing these components. Net taxes on production/imports for each NACE activity (j) are assumed to be proportional to its GVA - Eq. (23).

$$\begin{aligned} (T - S)_p^k &= \frac{GVA^j}{GVA} \cdot (T - S)_p \\ &= \frac{GOS^j + CE^j}{(GOS^E + CE^E) + (GOS^{NE} + CE^{NE})} \cdot (T - S)_p \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Net taxes on production/imports are allocated to income variables in the two-sector model based on the allocation of payments to capital and labor (e.g., Table 6).

Table 6

Allocation of payments to labor in the two-sector model, by NACE economic activity.

Two-sector model payments to labor	NACE economic activity
CE^E	A, B, C10–12, C19, D
CE^{NE}	All other NACE

4.2. Reclassification of energy/exergy balances

In addition to disaggregating national accounts (Section 4.1), we also analyze energy balances entering and exiting economic activities in the two-sector model.

Country-level energy balances are typically disaggregated by energy carrier and economic activity. This combination reveals energy consumption by activity and its origin. Conventional balances focus on primary and final energy flows, neglecting the useful stage and exergy content.

To obtain exergy balances at the final/useful stage, we use a 4-step methodology from (Serrenho et al., 2016) for each year and energy carrier (Ayres et al., 2003): 1) convert final energy data to exergy values; 2) allocate final exergy by activity/carrier to useful end-uses; 3) estimate 2nd law efficiencies for final-to-useful transformations; 4) calculate overall useful exergy by summing end-uses. Table 7 shows a simplified correspondence between energy carriers, economic activities, and useful end-use categories. The work of (Serrenho et al., 2016) extends conventional energy accounting to include food for humans, feed for working animals, and wind/water for mechanical drive.

A detailed list of all energy carriers, economic activities, and end-uses, and the correspondence between these three levels of disaggregation, is in Appendix B.

Once final and useful energy/exergy balances are disaggregated, they are allocated to energy/exergy flow variables in the two-sector model (Table 8). E-Sector own-uses ($E_{x,f}^{o-u}$, $E_{x,u}^{o-u}$) correspond to exergy consumption by conventional/supplement activities within that macro sector. Remaining useful exergy flows are either directly consumed by households/government – $(1 - \gamma) \bullet E_{x,u}$ – or used as inputs in NE-Sector production – $\gamma \bullet E_{x,u}$. The latter includes most industries, transport, and commercial services, while the former includes all residential consumption and a share of road transport (privately owned vehicles).

4.3. Useful exergy price estimates

The price for useful exergy in the two-sector model—whether for NE-Sector production or direct household/government consumption—is estimated by combining the disaggregation of macroeconomic national accounts with energy balances.

Useful exergy prices are estimated in two ways: 1) demand-side; 2) supply-side. The demand-side approach calculates the total useful exergy price ($p_{E_{x,u}}^{Demand}$) by summing direct household/government consumption expenditure on useful exergy (C^E) with intermediate payments (INT) and dividing by the total useful exergy flow out of the E-Sector

Table 7

Simplified 3-level disaggregation of final-to-useful energy/exergy flows (carrier, sector, end-use). Top row shows institutional sectors where final energy/exergy is consumed; Left column shows energy carriers; Other cells show useful energy/exergy end-uses.

	Industry	Transport	Other	Energy Industry own uses
Coal & coal products	High/medium/low heat	Mechanical drive	Low heat	Medium heat
Oil & oil products	High/medium/low heat	Mechanical drive	Mechanical drive	Medium heat
Natural gas	High/medium/low heat	Mechanical drive	Low heat	High/medium/low heat
Combustible renewables	Low heat	Mechanical drive	Low heat	–
Electricity & CHP heat	Various uses	Mechanical drive	Various uses	Various uses
Food & feed	–	–	Muscle work	–

Table 8

Allocation of energy balances to exergy flows in the two-sector model. (*) corresponds to the component in Chemical & petrochemical industries of Manufacture of coke & refined petroleum products. (†) corresponds to the component in Road transport of privately owned vehicles.

Two-sector model exergy flows	Economic activities
	Energy industry own uses
E-Sector own use $E_{x,f}^{o-u}, E_{x,u}^{o-u}$	Industry Chemical & petrochemical (*) Food & tobacco Other Agriculture & forestry Fishing Industry – except Chemical & petrochemical (*)
Inputs to NE-Sector production $\gamma \bullet E_{x,u}$	Transport – except Road (†) Commercial & public services Other Non-specified
Direct consumption by households/ government $(1 - \gamma) \bullet E_{x,u}$	Transport Road (†) Other Residential

($E_{x,u}$)—Eq. (24).

$$p_{E_{x,u}}^{Demand} = \frac{C^E + INT}{E_{x,u}} \tag{24}$$

Prices paid for useful exergy directly consumed by households/government ($p_{E_{x,u}}^{DC}$) – Eq. (1) – can be compared with prices paid for useful exergy by NE-Sector activities ($p_{E_{x,u}}^{INT}$) – Eq. (25). Eq. (24) is the weighed average of Eqs. (1) and (25), with weights γ and $(1 - \gamma)$, respectively.

$$p_{E_{x,u}}^{INT} = \frac{INT}{\gamma \bullet E_{x,u}} \tag{25}$$

Supply-side useful exergy prices are calculated by summing the gross value added (GVA) from conventional and supplement E-Sector activities (Fig. 3), E-Sector imports ($M^E = M_{Conv}^E + M_{Supp.}^E$), and the value of end-use devices converting final to useful exergy ($GVA_{imp.}^E = C_{imp.}^E = GOS^{E(Reclass.)}$). This total is then divided by the useful exergy output from the E-Sector ($E_{x,u}$)—Eq. (26).

$$p_{E_{x,u}}^{Supply} = \frac{GVA^E + M^E}{E_{x,u}} = \frac{(GVA_{Conv.}^E + GVA_{Supp.}^E + GVA_{Imp.}^E) + (M_{Conv.}^E + M_{Supp.}^E)}{E_{x,u}} \tag{26}$$

Comparing demand-side (Eq. 24) and supply-side (Eq. 26) price estimates for useful exergy serves as a consistency check on the model’s disaggregation and reclassification of macroeconomic national accounts and energy balances, with both measures expected to yield the same result.

When computing useful exergy prices, we exclude firewood burned in residential activities as it is typically not traded in the market. Therefore, we do not assign a price to this energy carrier and discount it from the energy balances before estimating useful exergy prices.

Estimated useful exergy prices reflect: 1) changes in aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency ($\varepsilon = E_{x,u}/E_{x,f}$); 2) changes in costs of man-made capital and labor in the extended energy sector; and 3) changes in final energy/exergy prices ($p_{Ex,f}$). Eq. (26) can be manipulated to isolate these effects in Eq. (27).

$$p_{E_{x,u}}^{Supply} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \bullet \left(1 + \frac{GVA_{FU}^E + GVA_{Imp.}^E}{GVA^E + M^E - GVA_{FU}^E - GVA_{Imp.}^E} \right) \bullet p_{Ex,f} \tag{27}$$

In the r.h.s., the first term represents the effect of aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency, the second term reflects the costs of capital and labor in converting exergy from the final to the useful stage, and the third term indicates the effect of final energy/exergy prices.

4.4. Application to Portugal 1960–2014: data

Annual time series data for Portugal comes from various sources, detailed in Appendix C. Most macroeconomic data is from AMECO (*Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO*, 2023), with more specific series from EUROSTAT (*European Statistical Office – EUROSTAT*, 2023), Banco de Portugal (*Novas Séries Longas para a Economia Portuguesa*, 2021), and EU KLEMS (*Stehrer and Sabouniha*, 2023). National accounts are disaggregated as described in Section 4, and most data is in nominal EUR values. Employment is measured by the number of individuals. As noted in (*Semienuik*, 2024), GDP measures undergo periodic structural revisions, including conceptual changes, which can affect growth rates and analysis outcomes. The GDP data used corresponds to the version available at the time of extraction (see (*Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO*, 2023)).¹⁵

Final and useful exergy balances are derived from the accounting work of (*Felício et al.*, 2019; *Serrenho et al.*, 2016). These datasets are based on final energy balances from the International Energy Agency (*IEA Energy Balances of OECD Countries*, 2025) for traditional energy carriers and supplemented with food intake data from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and (*Henriques*, 2011) on feed for working animals and other non-conventional energy carriers (e.g., wind).

Portugal is an ideal case study for our proposed two-sector framework. Over the last 50 years, the country has experienced significant improvements and stagnation in aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency (*Felício et al.*, 2019; *Serrenho et al.*, 2016). Previous analyses of Portuguese energy/exergy and economic data show a strong relationship between exergy efficiency and total factor productivity (*Santos et al.*, 2021), as well as between overall useful exergy consumption and economic growth (*Santos et al.*, 2018).

The final and useful exergy time series from (*Serrenho et al.*, 2016) are available only until 2009 but were updated to 2014 in (*Felício et al.*, 2019). Despite this limited data span, these references provide the highest quality final and useful exergy accounting studies specific to Portugal. Therefore, we choose to use these datasets for applying the proposed two-sector framework to the Portuguese economy.

5. Results and discussion

Section 4 outlined a method applicable to any country with available data. This section presents the main results from implementing the two-sector model in the Portuguese economy from 1960 to 2014. Sections 5.1 and 5.2 highlight selected results that illustrate the unique economic portrait produced by this framework, with additional results in Appendix C. Section 5.3 discusses the useful exergy price estimates for Portugal.

5.1. Characterising the two sectors

5.1.1. Expenditure

Fig. 6 illustrates the composition of expenditure in consumption (left) and investment (right) in each macro sector.

Most consumption expenditure is linked to NE-Sector goods and services. Over time, the share of direct E-Sector consumption expenditure slightly decreased, while the share of imputed rents from reclassified investments increased.

Most investment expenditure occurs in the NE-Sector, with a stable share. The share of E-Sector investment from reclassified consumption

¹⁵ Previous vintages of the data are available through the AMECO archive. These can be used, in future work, to assess the impact on our results from changing definitions of GDP, similarly to (*Semienuik*, 2024).

expenditure (e.g., communication and transport equipment, and other machinery – Table 4) is equal to the share from gross fixed capital formation (GFCF).

5.1.2. Factors of production

Fig. 7 illustrates the composition of capital (left) and labor (right) inputs in the two-sector model.

Most capital is in NE-Sector production, with the E-Sector comprising about 20 %, mainly from reclassified investment by the period's end. E-Sector capital stock is roughly double that of the conventional energy activities due to national account reclassification.

E-Sector employment was significant in 1960, driven by agriculture, but declined over time as NE-Sector employment grew.

5.1.3. Income

To provide some context to the historical behavior of payments to capital and labor in Portugal 1960–2014, Fig. 8 shows the share of these payments to each traditional factor of production, as reported in macroeconomic national accounts (*Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO*, 2023). The Democratic Revolution of 1974 in Portugal led to a dramatic fall in payments to capital. By the end of 1974, the share of payments to capital in value added had fallen from 23 % to 16 % (from 23 % in 1973), and would fall further to 5–6 % in 1975–76, rising again 1977, reaching its pre-revolution value in 1979–80. The reasons for this are detailed in Section 5.3.1 below.

Fig. 9 illustrates the payments to capital (left) and labor (right) in the two-sector model.

The share of payments to NE-Sector capital rose over recent decades, while E-Sector capital's share declined. However, E-Sector capital payments remain disproportionate to their stock relative to NE-Sector capital (Fig. 9). The 1974 peak in E-Sector payments from reclassified investment reflects the Democratic Revolution, which sharply reduced total payments to “traditional” capital.

Payments to labor mirror employment trends (Fig. 9), though E-Sector labor receives a smaller proportional share than NE-Sector labor.

Fig. 10 shows payment balances for capital and labor in both sectors. The E-Sector (left) is more capital-intensive than the NE-Sector (right). Over time, capital payments declined while labor payments rose, though recent years suggest a reversal.

5.2. Energy shares in each macro sector

Fig. 11 shows useful exergy flow shares allocated to two-sector model variables. E-Sector own-uses and residential firewood exergy are excluded from energy balances in price calculations.

The NE-Sector's share of useful exergy consumption has declined, while direct consumption has risen, reflecting increased reclassified capital for end-use energy devices in households and government.

5.3. Useful exergy price estimates

Demand-side useful exergy prices (nominal EUR) are calculated using Eq. (24). Supply-side prices for useful exergy direct consumption by households/government ($p_{Ex,u}^{DC}$) and intermediate consumption by the NE-Sector ($p_{Ex,u}^{INT}$) are derived from Eqs. (1) and (25). Overall supply-side prices use Eq. (26). Nominal prices are converted to real 2015 EUR using the GDP deflator from AMECO (*Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO*, 2023) – Fig. 12.

The top of Fig. 12 shows that the demand and supply approaches from Section 4.3 produce similar useful exergy price series, confirming the consistency of the reclassification in Section 4. Both series sharply decline in the first 15 years, experience a “bump” during the turbulent years after the Democratic Revolution (1975–79), and then decrease

Fig. 6. Expenditure in the two-sector model. Left: consumption expenditure (private and government); Right: investment expenditure (including reclassified investment in the E-Sector). C^{NE} and C^E denote consumption expenditure from national accounts for the NE and E sectors, respectively. $C^{E(imp.)}$ represents imputed rents from capital investment reclassified from consumption expenditure, as detailed in Section 4.1.3, allocated to the E-Sector. $I^{NE(GFCF)}$ and $I^{E(GFCF)}$ indicate investment expenditure from national accounts for the NE and E sectors, respectively, while $I^{E(P+G)}$ refers to investment reclassified from private and government consumption expenditure.

Fig. 7. Traditional inputs to production in the two-sector model. Left: capital stock; Right: human labor. $K^{NE(GFCF)}$ and $K^{E(GFCF)}$ are capital stocks allocated to NE and E sectors, respectively, while $K^{E(P+G)}$ comes from consumption expenditure. L^{NE} and L^E represent labor in NE and E sectors, respectively.

Fig. 8. Payments to traditional inputs to production in standard macroeconomic national accounts. Shares of value added. Payments to self-employed individuals counted as payments to labor. Source: (*Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO, 2023*).

more slowly until the 2000s, when they begin to rise again after the 2008 economic crisis.

The bottom of Fig. 12 shows that demand-side useful exergy prices for households/government are significantly higher than those for NE-Sector activities. Although these prices decreased drastically from 1960 to 2014, they remained about twice as high as NE-Sector prices by 2014 in real terms. Prior to the Democratic Revolution, both macro sectors' prices follow the same pattern (this is seen more clearly in the normalized prices in the bottom right of Fig. 12). NE Sector prices reveal a sharper drop during the revolutionary period compared to households/government. While NE-Sector prices rebounded after the revolution and eventually stabilized in the 1990s – see next section –, prices for

households/government continued to decline until the end of the period. The aggregation of these price series forms the demand-side useful exergy price estimates shown at the top of Fig. 12.

5.3.1. The revolutionary period: 1975–1979

In April 1974, the Portuguese armed forces staged a peaceful coup, overthrowing the right-wing authoritarian “Estado Novo” government that had ruled for nearly 50 years. This “Carnation Revolution” established a democratic government and led to the decolonization of African territories like Angola, Mozambique, and Cape Verde.

The impact of this revolutionary period is directly observed in macroeconomic time series (Krugman and de Macedo, 2019). It is also observed in the useful exergy price estimates obtained in this work.

In the early 70s, Portugal’s economy relied on imported oil, and the 1973 oil shock caused energy prices to soar – Fig. 12 (top). However, useful exergy prices dropped significantly between 1975 and 1979 due to the 1974 Democratic Revolution, which offset the oil shock’s effects. This revolution led to a sharp (but temporary) decline in the share of costs associated with manufactured capital (rents, gross operating surplus) and an increase in the share of labor costs (wages, salaries) (Lains, 2004) due to expanded labor rights, increased public employment, nationalization, capital flight, and rent controls. Figs. 9 and 10 illustrate these changes in the NE-Sector and E-Sector. The useful exergy price estimates in Fig. 12 reflect both final energy price changes and the costs

Fig. 9. Payments to traditional inputs to production in the two-sector model. Shares of value added. Left: gross operating surplus; Right: compensation of employees and self-employed. $GOS^{NE(GFCF)}$ and $GOS^{E(GFCF)}$ denote gross operating surplus from national accounts for the NE and E sectors, respectively. $GOS^{E(P+G)}$ represents surplus from reclassified consumption expenditure. CE^{NE} and CE^E are labor payments for the NE and E sectors.

Fig. 10. Payments to traditional factors of production in each sector. Shares of value added. Left: payments to capital (light grey) and labor (dark grey) in the NE-Sector; Right: payments to capital (lighter shades of grey) and labor (dark grey) in the E-Sector. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Useful exergy flows in the two-sector model. Left: including E-Sector own-uses and Residential Firewood; Right: only useful exergy output from the E-Sector (minus Residential Firewood). Shares of total (TeraJoule).

of capital and labor involved in energy conversion within the E-Sector¹⁶ - Eq. (27). Since the E-Sector is more capital-intensive, the reduction in capital costs after the revolution resulted in lower useful exergy prices, entirely offsetting the impact of rising oil prices during this period.

¹⁶ The possible endogeneity of the two effects deserves mention. While Portugal's Democratic Revolution stemmed from long-term structural weaknesses of the Estado Novo dictatorship—such as its authoritarian nature, colonial issues, and resistance to modernization—the rising energy prices from the 1973 oil shock also played a significant role as a catalyst for the revolution. The oil shock worsened existing economic difficulties, particularly the financial strain of colonial wars in Angola, Mozambique, and Guiné-Bissau, fueling dissatisfaction with the regime and bolstering momentum for the revolution.

After the Revolution, as political and economic stability returned and global market integration favored capital-intensive industries and private investments, payments to manufactured capital quickly rose to pre-1974 levels. Meanwhile, the lingering effects of the 1973 oil shock (and later the 1979 oil shock) continued to drive up final energy prices. These factors led to a sharp rise in useful exergy prices during this period (Fig. 12). Additionally, increased investment in low-efficiency energy-converting capital, such as personal automobiles, raised the cost per unit of useful exergy. Although significant improvements in aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency occurred post-revolution, their impact on useful exergy prices was offset by these other effects.

The methodology used in this paper to estimate useful exergy prices is sensitive to turbulent periods like the Portuguese Democratic

Fig. 12. Useful exergy price estimates. Top: Demand-side useful exergy prices (medium grey – Eq. (24)), supply-side useful exergy prices (dark grey – Eq. (26)), and Brent crude oil prices (light grey – source: (Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia, 2025)). Bottom left: Real demand-side prices faced by households/government (dotted line – Eq. (1)) and the NE-Sector (dashed line – Eq. (25)). Bottom right: Demand-side prices faced by households/government (dotted line) and the NE-Sector (dashed line) – normalized to initial year. All prices in real 2015 EUR/MJ. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Revolution. Specifically, costs of man-made capital are captured annually through gross operating surplus or consumption of fixed capital for each asset type and economic activity (see Section 4.1.3). Consequently, large fluctuations in payments to capital during the revolutionary period will introduce volatility in the useful exergy price estimates (see Figs. 9 and 10). Thus, our approach is not suitable for analyzing the relationship between useful exergy prices and economic growth during outlier years like 1975–1979 in Portugal. In the next section, we will discuss the results without considering this subperiod.

5.3.2. Useful exergy prices & economic growth

Table 9 presents average annual growth rates for useful exergy price, final-to-useful exergy efficiency and GDP. The revolutionary period of 1975–1979 is omitted from this table and subsequent analysis due to the reasoning outlined in the previous section.

Table 9 shows that useful exergy became significantly cheaper before the Democratic Revolution (1960–1974) for both households/government and NE-Sector activities (Fig. 10, bottom). This period was dominated by rapid efficiency improvements (average growth rate of 2.51 % per annum) driven by an electrification and industrialization process that began before 1960 (Serrenho et al., 2016). While increased efficiency contributed to lower prices, it wasn't the only factor. The E-Sector's replacement of labor with capital (by the increased share of industry vs. agriculture, and by changes in agriculture itself) also reduced the cost per unit of useful exergy generated. Together, these effects explain the decline in useful exergy prices during this period.

In the 1980s, an oil glut from falling demand during the 1970s oil crises halved oil prices by 1986 – Fig. 12 (top). However, in the early part of the decade, the effect of declining oil prices on useful exergy prices is partially offset by the effect of increasing capital costs that persisted until at least 1984. This period, marked by modest GDP growth (1.76 % per annum) and limited improvements in aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency (0.80 % per annum), was primarily driven by

the proliferation of low-efficiency energy-converting capital, such as automobiles, which raised the cost per unit of useful exergy.

In 1986, Portugal joined the European Economic Community (EEC), gaining access to the European market and funds for modernizing its infrastructure and economy. This, along with improved credit worthiness, lowered the costs of capital in the country. Adding to that the persisting effects of the oil glut, useful exergy prices declined significantly during this subperiod (2.37–2.41 % per annum). Consequently, although aggregate exergy efficiency increased slowly (0.39 % per annum), GDP grew significantly (4.84 % per annum).

From 1993 to 2014, the Portuguese economy shifted from recovery and growth to slow-down and stagnation. Although EU membership and adhesion to the euro provided benefits, structural weaknesses, competition from Chinese products after China's accession to the World Trade Organization, and high debt made the economy vulnerable, leading to the sovereign debt crisis. During this time, GDP growth and useful exergy prices stagnated, while improvements in aggregate exergy efficiency remained low, as they had since the mid-80s (0.32–0.43 % per annum). Overall, final energy prices rose during this period, due to liberalization of the energy market (electricity)¹⁷ and crude oil price increase – Fig. 12 (top). This had an upward effect on useful exergy prices. In 1993–2002, increases in final-to-useful exergy efficiency and declining costs of capital still managed to counter the effect of final energy prices, and so useful exergy prices decreased. However, between 2003 and 2014 useful exergy prices on average increased, due to lower

¹⁷ The liberalization of Portugal's electricity market, while designed to improve competition and efficiency, led to higher prices due to structural market issues, external dependencies, and policy decisions. Factors such as the phase-out of regulated tariffs, investments in renewables, exposure to international markets, and the tariff deficit were significant contributors to these price increases.

Table 9

Average growth rates for selected quantities in the Portuguese economy 1960–2014. Values are geometric means, with GDP reported in standard national accounts. Outlier years from 1975 to 1979 are excluded due to their anomaly following the Democratic Revolution, which disrupts overall economic trends.

	1960–1974	1975–1979	1980–1985	1986–1992	1993–2002	2003–2014	1960–2014
Gross Domestic Product	6.16 %	3.19 %	1.76 %	4.84 %	2.61 %	−0.12 %	3.21 %
Final-to-useful exergy efficiency	2.51 %	2.02 %	0.80 %	0.39 %	0.43 %	0.32 %	1.09 %
Useful exergy prices							
Demand	−2.36 %	−0.70 %	−0.47 %	−2.41 %	−1.32 %	0.36 %	−1.12 %
Supply	−2.29 %	−0.73 %	−0.02 %	−2.37 %	−1.29 %	1.35 %	−0.84 %

improvements in exergy efficiency, and increasing costs of energy-converting capital (e.g., the development of infrastructure for renewable energy in the country).

Table 9 shows that periods of rapid economic growth coincide with sharp declines in useful exergy prices (1960–1974, 1986–1992, 1993–2002), while slower GDP growth aligns with increases or slower decreases in useful exergy prices (1980–1985 and 2003–2014). This supports Robert Ayres and others’ argument that the declining real price of energy at the point of use is a key “engine of growth” (Ayres, 2001; Ayres and Warr, 2005; Ayres et al., 2003).

While previous research (Santos et al., 2021) indicates that changes in aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency correlate with long-run economic growth in Portugal (1960–2014), Table 9 shows that exergy efficiency alone cannot fully explain GDP changes across all subperiods. For instance, during 1980–1986, final-to-useful efficiency growth was double that of later periods (1986–1992; 1993–2002), yet GDP growth was significantly lower at 1.76 % compared to 2.61 % and 4.84 % in those later subperiods. Similarly, in 2002–2014, a positive average growth rate for final-to-useful exergy efficiency coincided with a negative GDP growth rate of −0.12 %.

By considering improvements in final-to-useful exergy efficiency along with changes in primary energy prices and the costs of capital and labor in the E-Sector, useful exergy price estimates more accurately reflect economic (GDP) growth across all subperiods.

Table 9 shows that a decline in useful exergy costs typically correlates with an increase in GDP across all periods. Subperiods with the highest average GDP growth rates—1960–1974 (6.16 %/annum, 2.29–2.36 % decrease in useful exergy prices) and 1986–1992 (4.84 %/annum, 2.37–2.41 % decrease)—also experienced significant decreases in useful exergy prices. In contrast, the only subperiod with negative GDP growth (−0.12 %/annum from 2003 to 2014) coincided with the only period with rising useful exergy prices (0.36–1.35 % increase).

The relationship between falling useful exergy prices and economic growth is further illustrated in Fig. 13 (left). Here, 5-year moving averages of annual growth rates for both useful exergy price (demand) and GDP are plotted against each other, excluding the outlier points of the revolutionary period (1974–1979).

The regression coefficient (−0.2991) in Fig. 13 (left) is statistically significant at the 1 % level, showing a negative correlation between changes in useful exergy price and GDP from 1960 to 2014 (excluding outliers from 1975 to 1979) in the Portuguese economy.

Fig. 13 (right) shows the positive correlation between annual growth rates for aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency and GDP, for the same years as Fig. 13 (left). The regression coefficient (0.2482) is also significant at the 1 % level. The coefficient of determination is larger than that of Fig. 13 (left). Comparing the two graphs, and with the information from Table 9, we argue that although aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency is a quantitatively better tracker of economic growth in Portugal, in the long-run, it fails to capture the qualitative changes in GDP throughout the period 1960–2014. On the other hand,

useful exergy prices – as estimated in this work – provide a qualitatively better tracker of economic growth, albeit quantitatively worse than exergy efficiency.¹⁸ By incorporating not only information on the changes to aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency, but also changes to the price of final energy/exergy and to the costs of capital/labor used in energy/exergy conversion to the useful stage, useful exergy prices are better equipped to describe changes to GDP in shorter periods.

While these observations suggest a need for a detailed analysis of the relationship between useful exergy prices and economic growth, this is beyond the current work’s scope. A broader approach should consider other factors and contextual elements (institutional, political, cultural) that may influence useful exergy price estimates. Additionally, potential endogeneity due to simultaneity and omitted variable bias must be addressed. Advanced statistical techniques are necessary to resolve these issues in future research.

6. Conclusions

This work presents a two-stage economic framework separating energy conversion from other productive activities. The extended energy macro sector covers all primary-to-useful energy conversions, measured via exergy, for consumers and non-energy activities.

The motivation for this approach is two-fold: 1) to develop a framework in which intermediate useful exergy is consistently treated as intermediate; 2) to implement this framework so as to obtain coherent and comprehensive estimates for the price of useful exergy. In the proposed two-sector framework, useful exergy is rightly recognized as an intermediate to production, generated from a combination of primary exergy flows, capital, and labor. Useful exergy price estimates obtained with our framework incorporate the effects of changes in: 1) final-to-useful exergy efficiency; 2) final energy/exergy prices; 3) capital-labor costs incurred in exergy conversion to a useful stage. In contrast to previous approaches (Grossman and Helpman, 1994; Henriques, 2011), our methodology is the first to consistently estimate a gauge for the aggregate price for energy services in the economy.

Implementing the two-sector framework, we detail a methodology for disaggregation and reclassification of national accounts and energy/exergy balances, mapping them onto the model’s variables. Consumption expenditure on final-to-useful exergy conversion end-use devices is reclassified as investment expenditure in the extended energy macro sector. Although here applied to Portugal 1960–2014, the proposed methods can be applied to any economy, adapting to data availability and granularity.

Our results reveal that Portugal’s extended energy macro sector has double the capital investment and stocks of the conventional energy activities, due to reclassification, while labor in the extended energy macro sector is proportionally less paid than in non-energy macro sector. Regarding useful exergy price estimates, all effects considered and excluding outlier years of the revolutionary period in Portugal, these can account for observed trends in long-run economic growth, (GDP). While aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency might provide a

¹⁸ Qualitative is here meant as relating to descriptions or characteristics not measured numerically and objectively compared (quantitative) but instead involving qualities, properties and subjective aspects.

Fig. 13. Annual growth rates for useful exergy price estimates (left) and aggregate final-to-useful exergy efficiency (right) versus annual growth rates for GDP, Portugal 1960–2014. Points represent 5-observation moving averages. Outliers from the 1975–1979 revolutionary period are excluded. The regression coefficients are significant at the 99 % confidence level. Useful exergy prices estimated from Eq. (24).

quantitatively better tracker for economic growth in the long-run, useful exergy prices offer a qualitatively better tracker. For Portugal, periods of decreasing useful exergy prices coincide with periods of faster economic growth, and vice-versa. The behavior of useful exergy prices supports the qualitative argument put forward by Robert Ayres, that their decline is a major driver of long-run economic growth (Warr and Ayres, 2012).

Further statistical analysis, such as panel regressions with instrumental variables (IV), is needed to clarify the link between useful exergy prices and GDP. This approach can identify suitable instruments, address endogeneity, and establish the causal relationship between exergy prices and economic growth. We can also compare results when the vintage for the GDP measure is changed, as in (Semieniuk, 2024).

Our framework serves as a basis for advanced models integrating energy/exergy flows with economic production. These models can enhance climate policy by incorporating emissions and waste. Expanding this analysis to other economies is now feasible with global energy/exergy databases (Marshall et al., 2024). Useful exergy price estimates can address data gaps in constructing gross output measures. While material flows are excluded here, they are crucial to environmental pressures (Schandl et al., 2016; Schandl et al., 2018). Integrating this model with a Material and Energy Metabolism Model for Economics (MEMME) is a future goal to achieve full-scale exergy accounting.

An important application of this work is estimating time-dependent useful exergy cost shares and adapting a CES production function to capture substitution between exergy and other factors (Stern and Kander, 2012). This can reveal exergy-specific technical parameters and insights into energy dependence, suggesting decoupling in advanced economies like Portugal may be less achievable than conventional models suggest.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

João Santos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tânia Sousa:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **André Serrenho:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Tiago Domingos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was supported by FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) through projects

UIDB/50009/2020, UIDP/50009/2020 and LA/P/0083/2020, as well as project “MAPS - Models, Assessment and Policies for Sustainability”, funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe program (contract no. 101137914).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Paul Brockway, Matthew Heun, Julian Salg, Gregor Semieniuk, Tim Foxon, and many of the participants in the International Exergy Economics workshops, for their constructive criticism on the conceptualization and application of the model presented here. We thank the consortium members of project “MAPS - Models, Assessment and Policies for Sustainability” for their valuable feedback. We also thank the anonymous reviewers for their constructive criticism and pertinent suggestions. This work is dedicated to the memory of Bob Ayres, who has inspired it, and encouraged the authors to pursue it from a very early stage in its development.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2025.108665>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abramovitz, M., 1956. Resource and output trends in the United States since 1870. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 46 (2), 5–23.
- Acs, Z., Estrin, S., Mickiewicz, T., Szerb, L., 2014. The Continued Search for the Solow Residual: The Role of National Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (No. 8652). Institute of Labor Economics (IZA).
- Aghion, P., Howitt, P., 2009. *The Economics of Growth*, vol. 1. The MIT Press.
- Aghion, P., Howitt, P., Brant-Collett, M., García-Peñalosa, C., 1998. *Endogenous Growth Theory*. MIT press.
- Allen, E.L., Cooper, C.L., Edmonds, F.C., Edmonds, J.A., Reister, D.B., Weinberg, A.M., Zelby, L.W., 1976. US energy and economic growth, 1975–2010 (No. ORAU/IEA-76-7). Institute for Energy Analysis, Oak Ridge, Tenn.(USA).

- Alvarez-Cuadrado, F., Van Long, N., Poschke, M., 2018. Capital-labor substitution, structural change and the labor income share. *J. Econ. Dyn. Control.* 87, 206–231.
- Annual Macro-economic Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs - AMECO. Version 2023-11-15 11:00. Available online at: https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/economic-research-and-databases/economic-databases/ameco-database_en#database.
- APS, 2008. Energy Future: Think Efficiency: How America Can Look within to Achieve Energy Security and Reduce Global Warming. American Physical Society.
- Aramendia, E., Brockway, P.E., Pizzol, M., Heun, M.K., 2021. Moving from final to useful stage in energy-economy analysis: a critical assessment. *Appl. Energy* 283, 116194.
- Ayres, R.U., 2001. The minimum complexity of endogenous growth models: the role of physical resource flows. *Energy* 26 (9), 817–838.
- Ayres, R., Voudouris, V., 2014. The economic growth enigma: capital, labour and useful energy? *Energy Policy* 64, 16–28.
- Ayres, R.U., Warr, B., 2005. Accounting for growth: the role of physical work. *Struct. Chang. Econ. Dyn.* 16 (2), 181–209.
- Ayres, R.U., Ayres, L.W., Martínás, K., 1998. Exergy, waste accounting, and life-cycle analysis. *Energy* 23 (5), 355–363.
- Ayres, R.U., Ayres, L.W., Warr, B., 2003. Exergy, power and work in the US economy, 1900–1998. *Energy* 28 (3), 219–273.
- Ayres, R.U., Savin, I., Bergh, J.V.D., Hao, L., 2022. Exergy versus labour in aggregate production functions: estimates for ten large economies. *Int. J. Exergy* 38 (3), 320–332.
- Bergeaud, A., Cette, G., Lecat, R., 2017. Total factor productivity in advanced countries: a long-term perspective. *Int. Product. Monit.* 32, 6.
- Berlemann, M., Wesselhöft, J.E., 2014. Estimating aggregate capital stocks using the perpetual inventory method: a survey of previous implementations and new empirical evidence for 103 countries. *Rev. Econ.* 65 (1), 1–34.
- Brockway, P.E., Barrett, J.R., Foxon, T.J., Steinberger, J.K., 2014. Divergence of trends in US and UK aggregate exergy efficiencies 1960–2010. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (16), 9874–9881.
- Brockway, P., Dewulf, J., Kjølstrup, S., Siebentritt, S., Valero, A., Whelan, C., 2016. In a resource-constrained world: Think exergy not energy. Report D/2016/13.324/5. Published by Science Europe, Brussels.
- Brockway, P.E., Heun, M.K., Santos, J., Barrett, J.R., 2017. Energy-extended CES aggregate production: current aspects of their specification and econometric estimation. *Energies* 10 (2), 202.
- Cleveland, C.J., 1992. Energy quality and energy surplus in the extraction of fossil fuels in the US. *Ecol. Econ.* 6 (2), 139–162.
- Cleveland, C.J., Costanza, R., Hall, C.A., Kaufmann, R., 1984. Energy and the US economy: a biophysical perspective. *Science* 225 (4665), 890–897.
- Costanza, R., 1992. *Ecological Economics: The Science and Management of Sustainability*. Columbia University Press.
- Costanza, R., Herendeen, R.A., 1984. Embodied energy and economic value in the United States economy: 1963, 1967 and 1972. *Resour. Energy* 6 (2), 129–163.
- Court, V., 2019. An estimation of different minimum exergy return ratios required for society. *BioPhys. Econ. Resour. Qual.* 4 (3), 11.
- Crafts, N., 2009. Solow and growth accounting: a perspective from quantitative economic history. *Hist. Polit. Econ.* 41 (Suppl. 1), 200–220.
- Dasgupta, P.S., Heal, G.M., 1979. *Economic Theory and Exhaustible Resources*. Cambridge University Press.
- Denison, E.F., 1962. Education, economic growth, and gaps in information. *J. Polit. Econ.* 70 (5, Part 2), 124–128.
- Denison, E.F., 1967. Sources of postwar growth in nine western countries. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 57 (2), 325–332.
- Denison, E.F., 2010. *Accounting for Slower Economic Growth: The United States in the 1970's*. Brookings Institution Press.
- Dincer, I., Rosen, M.A., 2012. *Exergy: Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development*. Newnes.
- Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia, 2025. Crude Oil Price Data. <https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/>.
- Doms, M., Dunne, T., 1998. Capital adjustment patterns in manufacturing plants. *Rev. Econ. Dyn.* 1 (2), 409–429.
- Easterly, W., Levine, R., 2001. What have we learned from a decade of empirical research on growth? It's not factor accumulation: stylized facts and growth models. *World Bank Econ. Rev.* 15 (2), 177–219.
- Eccelesia, M.V., Santos, J., Brockway, P.E., Domingos, T., 2022. A comprehensive societal energy return on investment study of Portugal reveals a low but stable value. *Energies* 15 (10), 3549.
- European Statistical Office – EUROSTAT, 2023. Available online at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/en/web/main/data/database#Legends>.
- Fabricant, S., 1954. Economic progress and economic change. In: *Economic Progress and Economic Change*. National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) 34th Annual Report. New York.
- Felício, L., Henriques, S.T., Serrenho, A., Domingos, T., Sousa, T., 2019. Insights from past trends in exergy efficiency and carbon intensity of electricity: Portugal, 1900–2014. *Energies* 12 (3), 534.
- Fouquet, R., 2011. Divergences in long-run trends in the prices of energy and energy services. *Rev. Environ. Econ. Policy* 5 (2), 196–218.
- Fouquet, R., 2014. Long run demand for energy services: income and price elasticities over two hundred years. *Rev. Environ. Econ. Policy* 8 (2), 186–207.
- Fouquet, R., 2016. Historical energy transitions: speed, prices and system transformation. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 22, 7–12.
- Fouquet, R., Pearson, P.J., 2006. Seven centuries of energy services: the Price and use of light in the United Kingdom (1300–2000) 1. *Energy J.* 27 (1), 139–178.
- Gallardo-Albarrán, D., Inklaar, R., 2021. The role of capital and productivity in accounting for income differences since 1913. *J. Econ. Surv.* 35 (3), 952–974.
- Gans, J., King, S., Libich, J., Byford, M., Mankiw, G., Stonecash, R., 2014. *Principles of Economics PDF*. Cengage Learning Australia.
- Georgescu-Roegen, N., 1971. *The Entropy Law and the Economic Process*. Harvard University Press.
- Gollier, C., 2013. *Pricing the Planet's Future: The Economics of Discounting in an Uncertain World*. Princeton University Press.
- Granger, C.W., 1969. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and cross-spectral methods. *Econometrica* 424–438.
- Griliches, Z., Jorgenson, D.W., 1966. Sources of measured productivity change: capital input. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 56 (1/2), 50–61.
- Grossman, G.M., Helpman, E., 1994. Endogenous innovation in the theory of growth. *J. Econ. Perspect.* 8 (1), 23–44.
- Guevara, Z., Sousa, T., Domingos, T., 2016. Insights on energy transitions in Mexico from the analysis of useful exergy 1971–2009. *Energies* 9 (7), 488.
- Haas, R., Nakicenovic, N., Ajanovic, A., Faber, T., Kranzl, L., Müller, A., Resch, G., 2008. Towards sustainability of energy systems: a primer on how to apply the concept of exergy services to identify necessary trends and policies. *Energy Policy* 36 (11), 4012–4021.
- Henriques, S., 2011. *Energy Transitions, Economic Growth and Structural Change: Portugal in a Long-Run Comparative Perspective*. In: *Lund Studies in Economic History*, 54. Lund University, Lund, Sweden.
- Heun, M.K., Santos, J., Brockway, P.E., Pruijm, R., Domingos, T., Sakai, M., 2017. From theory to econometrics to energy policy: cautionary tales for policymaking using aggregate production functions. *Energies* 10 (2), 203.
- Howarth, R.B., 1997. Energy efficiency and economic growth. *Contemp. Econ. Policy* 15 (4), 1–9.
- Hudson, E.A., Jorgenson, D.W., 1978. Energy prices and the US economy, 1972–1976. *Nat. Resour. J.* 18 (4), 877–897.
- Hulten, C.R., 2001. Total factor productivity: a short biography. In: *New Developments in Productivity Analysis*. University of Chicago Press, pp. 1–54.
- IEA Energy Balances of OECD Countries, 2025. Available online: <https://www.iea.org/statistics/balances/> (accessed on 4 January 2019).
- Jones, L.E., Manuelli, R., 1990. A convex model of equilibrium growth: theory and policy implications. *J. Polit. Econ.* 98 (5, Part 1), 1008–1038.
- Jorgenson, D.W., 1978. The role of energy in the US economy. *Natl. Tax J.* 31 (3), 209–220.
- Kander, A., Stern, D.I., 2014. Economic growth and the transition from traditional to modern energy in Sweden. *Energy Econ.* 46, 56–65.
- Kaufmann, R.K., 1992. A biophysical analysis of the energy/real GDP ratio: implications for substitution and technical change. *Ecol. Econ.* 6 (1), 35–56.
- Kendrick, J.W., 1961. *Productivity Trends in the United States*. Princeton University Press, Princeton NJ.
- King, C.W., 2020. *The Economic Superorganism*. Springer Nature.
- King, C.W., 2022. Interdependence of growth, structure, size and resource consumption during an economic growth cycle. *Biophys. Econ. Sustain.* 7 (1), 1.
- Koszerek, D., Havik, K., Mc Morrow, K., Röger, W., Schönborn, F., 2007. An overview of the EU KLEMS growth and productivity accounts. *Eur. Econ. Econ. Pap.* 2008–2015 (290).
- Krugman, P., de Macedo, J.B., 2019. The economic consequences of the April 25th revolution. In: *Portugal since the Revolution*. Routledge, pp. 53–87.
- Kümmel, R., 1989. Energy as a factor of production and entropy as a pollution indicator in macroeconomic modelling. *Ecol. Econ.* 1 (2), 161–180.
- Kümmel, R., Lindenberg, D., 2014. How energy conversion drives economic growth far from the equilibrium of neoclassical economics. *New J. Phys.* 16 (12), 125008.
- Kümmel, R., Lindenberg, D., Eichhorn, W., 2000. The productive power of energy and economic evolution. *Indian J. Appl. Econ.* 8 (2), 1–26.
- Kümmel, R., Schmid, J., Ayres, R.U., Lindenberg, D., 2008. Cost Shares, Output Elasticities, and Substitutability Constraints (No. 08, 02). EWI Working Paper.
- Kümmel, R., Ayres, R.U., Lindenberg, D., 2010. Thermodynamic laws, economic methods and the productive power of energy. *J. Non-Equilib. Thermodyn.* 35 (2), 145–179.
- Lains, P., 2004. The Portuguese economy in the twentieth century: growth and structural change. In: *Explorations in Economic Growth*. Aksant, Amsterdam.
- Lindenberg, D., Kummel, R., 2002. Energy-dependent production functions and the optimization model “PRISE” of price-induced sectoral evolution. *Int. J. Thermodyn.* 5 (3), 101–107.
- Mankiw, N.G., 1997. *Introduction to Macroeconomics*. Worth Publishing.
- Marshall, Z., Heun, M.K., Brockway, P.E., Aramendia, E., Steenwyk, P., Relph, T., et al., 2024. A Country-Level Primary-Final-Useful (CL-PFU) Energy and Exergy Database v1.2, 1960–2020. University of Leeds. <https://doi.org/10.5518/1199>.
- Mazzucato, M., 2011. The entrepreneurial state. *Soundings* 49 (49), 131–142.
- Meadows, D.L., Behrens, W.W., Meadows, D.H., Naill, R.F., Randers, J., Zahn, E., 1974. *Dynamics of Growth in a Finite World*. Wright-Allen Press, Cambridge, MA, p. 637.
- Nieto, J., Pollitt, H., Brockway, P.E., Clements, L., Sakai, M., Barrett, J., 2021. Socio-macroeconomic impacts of implementing different post-Brexit UK energy reduction targets to 2030. *Energy Policy* 158, 112556.
- Nordhaus, W.D., 1996. Do real-output and real-wage measures capture reality? The history of lighting suggests not. In: *The Economics of New Goods*. University of Chicago Press, pp. 27–70.
- Novas Séries Longas para a Economia Portuguesa, 2021. Version 2021-12-20. Banco de Portugal. Available online at: <https://bpstat.bportugal.pt/contedos/noticia/s/1498/>.
- Odhiambo, N.M., 2010. Energy consumption, prices and economic growth in three SSA countries: a comparative study. *Energy Policy* 38 (5), 2463–2469.

- Ozturk, I., 2010. A literature survey on energy–growth nexus. *Energy Policy* 38 (1), 340–349.
- Payne, J.E., 2010. A survey of the electricity consumption–growth literature. *Appl. Energy* 87 (3), 723–731.
- Pinto, R., Henriques, S.T., Brockway, P.E., Heun, M.K., Sousa, T., 2023. The rise and stall of world electricity efficiency: 1900–2017, results and insights for the renewables transition. *Energy* 269, 126775.
- Platchkov, L.M., Pollitt, M.G., 2011. The economics of energy (and electricity) demand. *Fut. Electr. Demand* 69 (17).
- Rebelo, S., 1991. Long-run policy analysis and long-run growth. *J. Polit. Econ.* 99 (3), 500–521.
- Reistad, G.M., 1975. Available energy conversion and utilization in the United States. *ASME J. Eng. Power* 97, 429–434.
- Romer, P.M., 1986. Increasing returns and long-run growth. *J. Polit. Econ.* 94 (5), 1002–1037.
- Sakai, M., Brockway, P.E., Barrett, J.R., Taylor, P.G., 2018. Thermodynamic efficiency gains and their role as a key ‘engine of economic growth’. *Energies* 12 (1), 110.
- Sala-i-Martin, X.X., Barro, R.J., 1995. Technological Diffusion, Convergence, and Growth (No. 735). Center discussion paper.
- Santos, J., Domingos, T., Sousa, T., Aubyn, M.S., 2018. Useful exergy is key in obtaining plausible aggregate production functions and recognizing the role of energy in economic growth: Portugal 1960–2009. *Ecol. Econ.* 148, 103–120.
- Santos, J., Borges, A.S., Domingos, T., 2021. Exploring the links between total factor productivity and energy efficiency: Portugal, 1960–2014. *Energy Econ.* 101, 105407.
- Schandl, H., Hatfield-Dodds, S., Wiedmann, T., Geschke, A., Cai, Y., West, J., Owen, A., 2016. Decoupling global environmental pressure and economic growth: scenarios for energy use, materials use and carbon emissions. *J. Clean. Prod.* 132, 45–56.
- Schandl, H., Fischer-Kowalski, M., West, J., Giljum, S., Dittrich, M., Eisenmenger, N., Fishman, T., 2018. Global material flows and resource productivity: forty years of evidence. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 22 (4), 827–838.
- Sciubba, E., 2019. Exergy-based ecological indicators: from thermo-economics to cumulative exergy consumption to thermo-ecological cost and extended exergy accounting. *Energy* 168, 462–476.
- Semieniuk, G., 2024. Inconsistent definitions of GDP: implications for estimates of decoupling. *Ecol. Econ.* 215, 108000.
- Semieniuk, G., Taylor, L., Rezai, A., Foley, D.K., 2021. Plausible energy demand patterns in a growing global economy with climate policy. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 11 (4), 313–318.
- Serrenho, A.C., Sousa, T., Warr, B., Ayres, R.U., Domingos, T., 2014. Decomposition of useful work intensity: the EU (European Union)-15 countries from 1960 to 2009. *Energy* 76, 704–715.
- Serrenho, A.C., Warr, B., Sousa, T., Ayres, R.U., Domingos, T., 2016. Structure and dynamics of useful work along the agriculture–industry–services transition: Portugal from 1856 to 2009. *Struct. Chang. Econ. Dyn.* 36, 1–21.
- Solow, R.M., 1956. A contribution to the theory of economic growth. *Q. J. Econ.* 70 (1), 65–94.
- Solow, R.M., 1957. Technical change and the aggregate production function. *Rev. Econ. Stat.* 39 (3), 312–320.
- Solow, R.M., 1962. Technical progress, capital formation, and economic growth. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 52 (2), 76–86.
- Solow, R.M., 1974. The economics of resources or the resources of economics. In: *Classic Papers in Natural Resource Economics*. Palgrave Macmillan UK, London, pp. 257–276.
- Sousa, T., Domingos, T., 2006a. Equilibrium econophysics: a unified formalism for neoclassical economics and equilibrium thermodynamics. *Physica A* 371 (2), 492–512.
- Sousa, T., Domingos, T., 2006b. Is neoclassical microeconomics formally valid? An approach based on an analogy with equilibrium thermodynamics. *Ecol. Econ.* 58 (1), 160–169.
- Sousa, T., Brockway, P.E., Cullen, J.M., Henriques, S.T., Miller, J., Serrenho, A.C., Domingos, T., 2017. The need for robust, consistent methods in societal exergy accounting. *Ecol. Econ.* 141, 11–21.
- Stanton, E.A., Ackerman, F., Kartha, S., 2009. Inside the integrated assessment models: four issues in climate economics. *Clim. Dev.* 1 (2), 166–184.
- Stehr, R., Sabouniha, A., 2023. *Growth and Productivity Database*. Version: January 2023. The Vienna Institute for International Economic Studies (Wiiw). Available online at <https://euklems.eu/>.
- Stern, D.I., Kander, A., 2012. The role of energy in the industrial revolution and modern economic growth. *Energy J.* 33 (3), 125–152.
- Swan, T.W., 1956. Economic growth and capital accumulation. *Econ. Rec.* 32 (2), 334–361.
- Tintner, G., Deutsch, E., Rieder, R., Rosner, P., 1977. A production function for Austria emphasizing energy. *De Economist* 125 (1), 75–94.
- Toda, H.Y., Yamamoto, T., 1995. Statistical inference in vector autoregressions with possibly integrated processes. *J. Econ.* 66 (1–2), 225–250.
- Tostes, B., Henriques, S.T., Brockway, P.E., Heun, M.K., Domingos, T., Sousa, T., 2024. On the right track? Energy use, carbon emissions, and intensities of world rail transportation, 1840–2020. *Appl. Energy* 367, 123344.
- US Energy Information Administration (US EIA), 2011. *Energy consumption, expenditures, and emissions indicators estimates, selected years, 1949–2011*. In: *US Energy Information Administration: Annual Energy Review 2011*. Available online at http://www.eia.gov/totalenergy/data/annual/pdf/sec1_13.pdf.
- van Ark, B., 2014. *Total Factor Productivity: Lessons from the Past and Directions for the Future* (No. 271). National Bank of Belgium.
- Warr, B., Ayres, R., 2006. REXS: a forecasting model for assessing the impact of natural resource consumption and technological change on economic growth. *Struct. Chang. Econ. Dyn.* 17 (3), 329–378.
- Warr, B.S., Ayres, R.U., 2010. Evidence of causality between the quantity and quality of energy consumption and economic growth. *Energy* 35 (4), 1688–1693.
- Warr, B., Ayres, R.U., 2012. Useful work and information as drivers of economic growth. *Ecol. Econ.* 73, 93–102.
- Warr, B., Schandl, H., Ayres, R.U., 2008. Long term trends in resource exergy consumption and useful work supplies in the UK, 1900 to 2000. *Ecol. Econ.* 68 (1–2), 126–140.
- Weitzman, M.L., 1998. Recombinant growth. *Q. J. Econ.* 113 (2), 331–360.
- Whiting, K., Carmona, L.G., Sousa, T., 2017. A review of the use of exergy to evaluate the sustainability of fossil fuels and non-fuel mineral depletion. *Renew. Sust. Energy Rev.* 76, 202–211.